

Least squares approximation of ECG signals with rational functions

Software_05: *.m (GNU Octave)

Kobzos, Laszlo

zehu.kola.ci@gmail.com

1. Abstract

We have reached the end of the presentation of our programs. In this article, we describe the framework program and its subprograms written in GNU Octave [9]. First, we discuss the framework program and the initial steps of wave approximation. In the next section, we describe the possibilities for refining the approximations. Since all program parts are elements of the FEX3 program system, we strongly recommend reviewing our 8 articles [1...8] so far. If something is not clear, in any part of the program, we recommend translating our Hungarian comments into English - e.g. with Google Translate. All our articles are easily accessible, in chronological order: <https://zenodo.org/search?q=Kobzos&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=oldest> We have of course tested the FEX3 program system in another library as well. Except for compiled Fortran programs, because they probably wouldn't work in a different environment.

2. ppp.m and the "beginning" („kezdő”) program parts of the approximation of each wave

If we have executed the **prep** program [5], then the **oneper** program [6], and the **pr50Hz** program [6 and 4], which filters network noise, then the necessary files for approximations with rational fractional functions are ready.

You also need to set two user environment variables: the value of **XYZ1** to 1, 2 or 3 depending on whether we have now selected the X, Y or Z lead, and the value of **FILT2** to 0 or 1 depending on whether we want to use the 99Hz filter (0=no, 1=yes) {[8] 3.2. *Lines of blocks*, Input UNITs:, command line parameters:, third line}. For example, to start the approximate program **progr1-123** (whose name after compilation is: **ures.exe**), the following are required: **ures.exe %XYZ1% Oct %FILT2%**. The easiest way to set these two variables is with the **qqq.bat** batch program (See Attachments:). Of course, the framework will launch the **ures.exe** program.

The exception is the **Octa\hely_bazis-nb_pont_.txt** file. This includes, for example, the number of points in the ECG signal. Therefore, for every new **Stream.XYZ** (once we have completed the above steps), this file must also be configured. To do this, the content of the data file corresponding to the ECG lead corresponding to the value of **XYZ1** must be deleted (since this **adat_file-×_u.txt** still contains the values of the previous **Stream.XYZ** data). Then a single 0 (zero) character must be entered into the file. Starts a new instance of the command interpreter, **Cmd.exe**. Then, for example, if we extracted the attached compressed file to the **T:\ABC** directory, then in this window (alias DOS window), set "**T:\ABC\ECG-test2**" to be the current directory. In this, you need to run the **ures.exe %XYZ1% Exc %FILT2%** program. Note: This does NOT need to be done for the other two leads.

Set the "**Current Directory**" of the **GNU Octave GUI** to the **Octa** subdirectory, as this is where all **Octave** programs are located. Since we used a relative directory structure in all programs (Fortran, Octave), the structure must be maintained. For example, if we extracted the attached compressed file to the **T:\ABC** directory, then the current directory should be **T:\ABC\ECG-test2\Octa**.

Now we can start the **ppp.m** framework.

After setting some initial values, the **ppp.m** framework program executes the **pp_kk.m** program section. This examines the data file ("**adat_file-x_u.txt**") belonging to the current ECG lead to see how far we have come in the processing. Based on this, we decide what the next step should be. Currently - since we have just started processing an ECG lead - we choose the option "**1. új adat_file-t kezd**" = "1. Start new data file". This is done in a pop-up window displayed by **listdlg**. See the attached HU==>EN translation "**pp_kk_textek_HU_EN.txt**". Of course, we have translated all on-screen text into English, in the entire "**FEX3**" program system. In a few places, e.g. where the "**disp** function" does the output, we were unable to output Hungarian characters with Hungarian accents, as Octave does not support the output of national characters. ("National alphabets are not supported.")

Since the choice was "1. új adat_file-t kezd", the **ppp.m** framework program calls the **pppK9.m** program section. Which sets the initial drawing data, then after drawing the original ECG lead, calls the **pppK8.m** program section. Using a **menu** function, we can choose which wave will be the starting wave in a pop-up window: the Ta or the P.

If we choose the Ta wave, then the method of approximating it has already been described in section {[8]09~ ~~~ chapter}. By looking at the old and new drawings, we can decide whether the approximation is appropriate. If not, let's start over. If appropriate, after comparing the drawings, select the **last** (in this case the second) **drawing** ("in focus") and press the ENTER (RET) key on the keyboard. The program then advances to the P wave.

If there was no Ta wave, then the initial approximation of the P wave starts immediately. This is handled by the **pppK1.m** program section. Note: in the names of our Octave programs, the letter **K** stands for the Hungarian Start (Kezdet): e.g. **pppK1.m**. Our only task here is to mark the beginning and end of the P wave on the drawing. Then the program makes 2+1 approximation steps using the ures.exe program. The two steps add two pairs of poles to the denominator. The +1 will be a copyback step and an approximation.

Then the FEX3 system returns to the **ppp.m** framework program and there, on line 224, in a pop-up window displayed by another **listdlg**, we can choose whether to "1. folytatjuk = continue" the approximation or "2. befejezzük... = finish...". If we "**continue**", then one of the **pppF^x.m** program parts will follow. Note: in the names of our Octave programs, the letter **F** stands for the Hungarian Continuation (Folytatás): e.g. **pppF1.m**.

If we choose "finish", then the **ppp.m** framework program asks another question on line 301: "A programban bent maradunk? = Do we stay in the program?" If we choose "Nem = No", then the program is temporarily exited. Namely, the program jumps to the "Végrajz = Final drawing" section, but it actually creates 2 drawings only when all waves have been completed. If we choose "Igen = Yes", then the approximation of the next wave starts. When we want to continue the program again, after the temporary exit, we simply have to restart the **ppp.m** framework program. What is described in these two paragraphs does not only happen when approximating the P wave, but also when approximating any other wave.

The "Folytatás = continuation" sections are discussed below.

The next wave will be T. The data file **adat_file-x_u.txt** is set by the **pppK3.m** program section. The options have already been discussed here: {[8] 3. Program Description | 13~ ~~~ chapter}. In the referenced description, we discussed 4 cases. There are only 3 cases in the program: the 3rd and 4th cases in the description

have been merged in the program. That is, if only one broken line were enough instead of the two parts, then one line should be the continuation of the other. After marking points 1, 2, 3, later the end point of the T wave will also need to be marked on the diagram.

The initial step of QRS approximation is handled by the **pppK1.m** program section described for the P wave, with minor differences.

The differences:

- The name of the wave written in the texts is different.
- The data is taken from different lines of the form file ("..\AUXX\adat_file-ures.txt"), and the number of parameters is different.
- The value of the main coefficient **d** in the initial parameter line is larger.
- The number of initial approximations is 3+1 instead of 2+1.

3. “Continuation” („folytatás”) program parts of the wave approximation

The **ppp.m** framework program performs the approximations of 1 lead. So, when approximating a new ECG lead, the **ppp.m** framework program must be restarted, but before that, the XYZ1 and FILT2 environment variables must be set. An inner cycle handles the individual waves. A cycle within this cycle sets the parameters of the individual waves.

In the innermost loop, we can choose from 4 program parts, and we can select this in a pop-up window displayed by **listdlg**:

0. készen vannak, a közelítés futtatása jön
1. "Nevező"
2. "Számológép" (ha ELŐTTE megvolt a paraméterek visszamásolása?)
3. "Súly"
4. "CIKLUSBAN"
5. "rövid CIKLUSBAN"

That is:

0. are ready, the approximation run is next
1. "Denominator"
2. "Counter" (if there was a copyback of the parameters BEFORE?)
3. "Weight setting"
4. "IN CYCLE"
5. "In SHORT CYCLE"

There is no program associated with 0 because we have already set the parameters for the next approximation, i.e. we exit the innermost cycle here. The program section **pppF1.m** is associated with the choice of 1, the program section **pppF2.m** is associated with the choice of 2, the program section **pppF3.m** is associated with the choice of 3, while the program section **pppF4.m** is associated with the choice of 4 and 5.

3.1. Denominator (Nevező) (pppF1.m)

The program part mainly deals with the parameter line denominator, but not exclusively. In a pop-up window displayed by **listdlg**, we can choose what the next step should be:

AZ ÚJ PARAMÉTER-SOR LEGYEN:

1. a közelítés eredménye VISSZAMÁSOLva (COPYBACK)
2. - " - ÉS a nevező BŐVÍTVE
3. BACKSTEP egy régebbi közelítéshez (pl.:CIKLUSBAN után)
4. a futás ELŐTTI paraméter-sorban, a nevező BŐVÍTVE

That is:

LET THE NEW PARAMETER LINE BE:

1. the result of the approximation is COPYBACK
2. - " - AND the denominator EXPANDED
3. BACKSTEP to an older approximation (e.g. after "IN CYCLE")
4. old parameter line BEFORE the run, then EXPANDING the denominator

If you choose 1 or 2, you will be asked another question:

A SZÁMLÁLÓ paraméterei:

1. a VISSZAMÁSOLT (COPYBACK) ÚJ közelítés értékei legyenek
2. MARADJANAK az ELŐZŐ paraméter-sor értékei

That is:

COUNTER parameters:

1. let the values of the COPYBACK NEW approximation be
2. KEEP the values of the PREVIOUS parameter row

We will discuss the case of choosing option 3 in more detail. If we want to return to the previous parameter set with a few approximations, either because the last approximation only approximates the noise better, or because we want to improve the approximation in another direction, this is possible. This helps with:

- the value of the previous `fajt12` variables,
- the value of the standard deviations and
- the serial numbers.

If we did not use the "IN CYCLE" ("CIKLUSBAN") approximation, the output would look like this:

11	89.38	1
12	71.44	2
13	68.52	3
13	68.52	4

Here, the first column contains the values of **fajt12**, the second column contains the values of the **standard deviations**, and finally, the third column contains the **serial numbers** of the previous drawings and saved parameters of the wave being approximated.

If we used the "IN CYCLE" ("CIKLUSBAN") approximation, the output would look like this:

11	79.64	1
12	63.92	2
13	61.38	3
13	61.38	4

fajt	szoras	S/N		fajt	szoras	S/N	
13	61.38	5	V =	13	61.38	8	V
14	61.01	6	V =	14	61.01	9	V
15	60.19	7	V >	15	60.04	10	V

Here the first four lines contain the part before the "IN CYCLE" approximation. The last three rows contain the "IN CYCLE" approximation, the 3-3 columns of which are similar. The first 3 columns are the type 1 approximations (see below 3.4. "IN CYCLE" and...), while the second 3 columns are the values of the type 2 approximations. In the fourth and ninth columns, the letters V indicate if the standard deviation below the row is smaller, meaning the approximation has improved. Between the two parts, the middle column compares the values of the standard deviations of the two types of approximation: with =, <, > signs, with their usual meanings.

Based on what has been done so far, we can select which approximations we would like to view. If we have already selected which approximation we would like to return to based on these figures, the following figure will appear:

Once the selection is made, all drawings will disappear except the one we selected. At the same time, the selected saved parameters will be written back to the parameter line by the program (therefore, no copyback is needed here). Then this must be run by selecting "0. are ready, the approximation will run" ("0. készen vannak, a közelítés futtatása jön").

3.2. Counter (Számláló) (pppF2.m)

The program part mainly deals with the parameter line counter, but not exclusively. In the pop-up window displayed by **listdlg**, we can choose what the next step should be:

A ZÉRUSOK bevitele:

1. valós Z 1 db.
2. valós Z 2 db.
3. valós Z x db. (Későbbi fejlesztés lesz!!!)
4. komplex Z pár (csak)
5. komplex Z pár+kxPÓLUSpár (Egyirányú)

6. komplex Z pár+kxPÓLUSpár (Alternáló)

That is:

1. real Z 1 piece
2. real Z 2 pieces
3. real Z ? pieces (Will be a later development!!!)
4. complex Z pair (only)
5. complex Z pair+cxPOLE pair (One-way)
6. complex Z pair+cxPOLE pair (Alternating)

The first two choices represent the real zeros, i.e., mark where the signal intersects the baseline. After the execution of the **pppK1.m** program section, the denominator of the P wave is fourth degree. So, it is worth being careful to only enter fewer than 4 zeros at a time, because otherwise the approximating function will not be a real fraction. This means that the ECG wave will not approach the baseline at either end. So, it is advisable to enter the zeros in two steps and perform a denominator expansion between them. That is, in program section *3.1. Denominator (Nevező) (pppF1.m)*, after the heading "THE NEW PARAMETER LINE SHOULD BE (AZ ÚJ PARAMÉTER-SOR LEGYEN):" select option 2. (In the QRS approximation, the initial denominator is a sixth power instead of a fourth power.)

Notes:

- In the **fajt12** specifications, the second number is the number of **pole pairs**, so twice this is the degree of the denominator.
- If we mark an odd number of zeros, there will be a first-degree and the rest will be merged into zero pairs by the program. If we then enter a single new zero, the first-degree will disappear and a new zero pair will appear in the parameter row.

We have already described the cases of choices 4, 5 and 6: {[3] 2e and 4e}.

3.3. Weight (Súly) (pppF3.m)

We already wrote about this in sections {[8] 3.2. Lines of blocks} and {[3] 4.11. Problems and their practical solutions}. After marking the starting and ending points of the weighting, the weight value can be set. If we want to stop the weighting, we set the weight to 1.00. Currently, the program can only change the first weighting row.

3.4. IN CICLE ("CIKLUSBAN") and "In SHORT CYCLE" ("rövid CIKLUSBAN") (pppF4.m)

Here we are expanding the denominator in cycles.

For type 1 approximations in a cycle:

- copyback the parameters of the previous run result from the backup,
- expanded it,
- but without changing the values of the zeros,

- finally runs the approximation program (**ures.exe**).

For type 2 approximations in a cycle:

- extends the **original** parameter line without copyback,
- finally runs the approximation program (**ures.exe**).

Experience shows that the two methods generally give the same results, but there are times when one or the other results in a better approximation.

The only difference between "IN CYCLE" ("CIKLUSBAN") and "In SHORT CYCLE" ("rövid CIKLUSBAN") is:

- the "IN CYCLE" ("CIKLUSBAN") run lasts until the maximum number of poles, while
- the "In SHORT CYCLE" ("rövid CIKLUSBAN") only executes 3 cycles (of course, if it is greater than the maximum number of poles, then until then).

4. Functions

data_r.m	reads data from " adat_file-×_u.txt "
setPQRST_1.m	stores the wave number (as a character), for getPQRST_1.m
getPQRST_1.m	returns the wave number (as a character)
adat_eddig.m	for the pp_kk.m program part: analyzes the content of " adat_file-×_u.txt ", where are we in the approximation
rajz.m	creates a drawing from the data in rajz-rr.txt or rajz-uu.txt (and renamed copies of these)
i_tart.m	how many lines does the " adat_file-×_u.txt " block contain? {[8] 3.1. <i>Block structure of parameter file</i> }
E10_4.m	converts the row vector of values into a character sting of the form "Fortran n(1X,E10.4)"
urlap_r.m	reads from " ../AUXX/data_file-ures.txt " (form template)
raj_zv.m	once the approximation of all the waves of the ECG lead is complete, 2 drawings of the results are made (final drawings)

5. Comments, experiences

Drawings are always placed in the same place on the screen. We usually only keep two drawings. That is, with a new drawing, the older one always disappears. For example: the first one disappears, and the second and third ones are visible. Of course, after the "4. IN CYCLE" ("4. CIKLUSBAN") or "5. In SHORT CYCLE" (5. "rövid CIKLUSBAN"), all drawings (max. 10) selected in the "3. BACKSTEP to an older..." (3. BACKSTEP egy régebbi...) section will be retained. Once you have reviewed the drawings, you must select the last drawing and press ENTER to continue.

Anyone who has used Octave will know how to enlarge a detail in the magnifier with a + sign. However, you can only select points if you click on the magnifier with the + sign again to reset it. Then the magnifier disappears and the cursor returns to the large + sign.

We are using a 1920×1080 resolution monitor. If your monitor is not of this size, you can set the **ppp.m** program to have a different size for the drawings by changing the *mpozic* values.

If the figure has a title, it can be of the following two forms:

rajz-rr fajt = 12 AZONOSÍTÁSI IDŐ:250506 192033

VegRajz-y-002.txt AZONOSÍTÁSI IDŐ:250506 193707

For approximations, rajz-rr denotes the drawing of the approximation, fajt = 12 see: "*3.1. Denominator* (pppF1.m)", and **AZONOSÍTÁSI IDŐ** is the timestamp.

The final drawing is indicated by **VegRajz-y-002.txt**, where y represents the ECG lead, and 002 indicates that the 2nd of the 5 designated periods was approximated{[6] "ciklus.txt" descriptions}.

The standard deviation of the approximations is written in the upper right corner of the drawings, for example: $\sigma = 33.09$

Fortran programs need to be recompiled because the environment may be different. That is why we did not include the compiled programs in the **ECG-222.zip** file. The **progr1-compile---. bat** in **ECG-test.zip** in [8] can help with the compilation.

Attachments:

ppp_blks_grid_nem3.pdf	ppp block schema
ppp_blk_HU_EN.rtf	ppp block schema translation
ppp_textek_HU_EN.txt	ppp Indító keretpogrogram = Starter for framework program
pppK1_textek_HU_EN.txt	pppK1 P and QRS
pppK3_textek_HU_EN.txt	pppK3 T
pppK5_textek_HU_EN.txt	pppK5 Ta
pppF1_textek_HU_EN.txt	pppF1 Nevező = denominator
pppF2_textek_HU_EN.txt	pppF2 Számláló = Numerator
pppF3_textek_HU_EN.txt	pppF3 Súly = Weight
pppF4_textek_HU_EN.txt	pppF4 Ciklusban = In cycle
pp_kk_textek_HU_EN.txt	pp_kk for analyzing the current data_file-×_u.txt
ECG-222.zip	all files
descript.ion	descript.ion
Fig01.jpg	final drawing1
Fig02.jpg	final drawing2

In the upper left corner of the **Fig01.jpg** drawing:

Filt2Erdt = original signal and filter 2 was on

Approx = the approximate signal

Err230731 = the error + noise, the first 6 characters of the timestamp

BL161647 = the baseline, the second 6 characters of the timestamp

1mV = 1mV

In the upper left corner of the **Fig02.jpg** drawing:

P
Ta
QRS
T
V--idx 4 = length of the signal vectors, the 4th of the 5 selected periods was approximated
1mV

6. References

- [1] Kobzos, L. (2022). FEX3-ECG/Charts01: Least Squares Approximation of ECG Signals with Rational Functions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6479410>
- [2] Kobzos, L. (2022). FEX3-ECG/Charts02: Least Squares Approximation of ECG Signals with Rational Functions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7365661>
- [3] Kobzos, L. (2023). FEX3-ECG/MS01,v1.0.4: Least Squares Approximation of ECG Signals with Rational Functions (1.0.4). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7671387>
- [4] Kobzos, L. (2024). FEX3-ECG/PREP01,v1.0.0: Least Squares Approximation of ECG Signals with Rational Functions (1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10701069>
- [5] Kobzos, L. (2024). FEX3-ECG/SW01 prep.f95: Least Squares Approximation of ECG Signals with Rational Functions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13765355>
- [6] Kobzos, L. (2024). FEX3-ECG/SW02 oneper.f95: Least Squares Approximation of ECG Signals with Rational Functions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14013435>
- [7] Kobzos, L. (2024). FEX3-ECG/SW03 prep3_b.f95: Least Squares Approximation of ECG Signals with Rational Functions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14569150>
- [8] Kobzos, L. (2025). FEX3-ECG/SW04 progr1-123.f95: Least Squares Approximation of ECG Signals with Rational Functions (Verzió v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15068057>
- [9] John W. Eaton, David Bateman, Søren Hauberg, Rik Wehbring (2019).
GNU Octave version 8.2.0 manual: a high-level interactive language for numerical computations.
URL <https://docs.octave.org/v8.2.0/>
Octave was configured for "x86_64-w64-mingw32".